

CLASSIFICATION OF HIGHWAYS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN ACCORDING TO THEIR AFFILIATION AND ECONOMIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE NATURE

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In today's conditions of globalization and urbanization, the development of transport infrastructure, in particular highways, is recognized as one of the most important factors of the country's economic development. A number of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have identified the modernization of highways and their bringing them up to international standards as a priority. At the same time, the need to attract sufficient financial resources for the development of public highways, their effective management and legal regulation is becoming an urgent issue. This requires improving theoretical approaches to financing highways and developing modern organizational and legal mechanisms.

Edward Glaeser¹ (2011) has analyzed the relationship between urban development and transport infrastructure, showing that investments in road networks strengthen inter-city economic connections and increase transport efficiency. He also explains the role of transport infrastructure investments in urbanization.

Jeffrey Sachs² (2015) has highlighted the importance of financing sustainable infrastructure development, in particular environmentally friendly and socially inclusive road networks. He highlights the opportunities offered by international donors, green bonds and impact investments.

Antonio Estache³ (2010) is one of the leading experts in infrastructure economics, and his research has raised the issue of optimal allocation of resources in financing road infrastructure through subsidies, pricing policies and user fees.

N. Nabieva⁴ (2020) studied the practice of financing infrastructure projects in Uzbekistan based on the public-private partnership (PPP) model.

¹ Glaeser, E. (2011). *Triumph of the city: How urban spaces make us human*. Pan Macmillan.

² Sachs, J. D. (2015). *The age of sustainable development*. Columbia University Press.

³ Estache, A. (2010). *Infrastructure finance in developing countries: An overview*. EIB Papers, 15(2), 60-88.

⁴ Nabieva, N. (2020). *Ўзбекистон Республикаси йўл-транспорт инфратузилмасини инновацион ривожлантириш*.

She analyzed the problems and opportunities of involving the private sector in financing road projects in Uzbekistan.

The legal basis for regulating social relations in the field of development and use of highways in the Republic of Uzbekistan is determined by the Law "On Highways".

First of all, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of "highway". A highway is a complex of engineering structures built in accordance with state standards, ensuring the safe and comfortable movement of vehicles of specified weight and dimensions.

Figure 1. Highways of the Republic of Uzbekistan by their affiliation and economic and administrative nature.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, highways are divided into public roads, urban and other populated areas roads, and enterprise (specialized) roads, depending on their affiliation.

Public highways are roads registered in accordance with the procedure established by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, having an index and serial number. These roads are divided into the following categories depending on their role in the national economy and administrative significance: roads of international, state, and local (regional) importance.

International highways are roads that connect the capitals of independent states and are included in international transport networks on the basis of international agreements. They are of strategic importance in ensuring regional cooperation and economic integration. At the same time, roads of state importance include roads that provide transport between the administrative, cultural and industrial centers of the republic and regions, and connect these centers with railway stations, ports, ship berths, as well as with neighboring countries. Local roads include roads that connect the administrative centers of the

republic and regions with the administrative centers of districts, with rural settlements, as well as district centers with roads of republican importance, railway stations, ports, ship berths. It is worth noting that the list of highways of state and local (regional) importance is approved by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while the list of highways of international importance is approved on the basis of agreements between states.

In conclusion, the stable and rapid growth of the country's economy largely depends on the quality of roads and the level of development of road transport infrastructure. Modern road networks play a crucial role in strengthening economic ties, strengthening interregional cooperation and stimulating the functioning of the internal market. In this regard, the development of transport infrastructure is one of the strategic factors of economic growth.

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